

LINGUISTICS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

Berdiyeva Gulshirin

Academic lyceum under Termez state university

gulshirin505@gmail.com

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Abstract. The article discusses that language plays an outstanding role among other phenomena in real life aspects. Various branches of linguistics and its components are listed and analyzed.

Key words: linguistics, English language, student, teacher, higher educational institutions.

In learning any language, it is important to pay attention to a number of its components. This also applies to linguistics. The term linguistics comes from the Latin word *lingua*, which means "language". Therefore, linguistics is the science that studies language. It gives information about how language stands out among other phenomena of reality, what are its elements and units, how and what changes occur in the language. Linguistics of the English language explores the structures and patterns of a given language, its functioning and development, and also compares with other languages to identify links with it.

Linguistics is general and particular. General linguistics - examines, examines and compares all the languages of the world as a whole. Private linguistics considers only one specific language. In our case, English. Linguistics is subdivided into scientific linguistics and practical linguistics. Most often, linguistics refers to scientific linguistics. Linguistics is part of semiotics as a science of signs. Hence, linguistics is a generalization of all sciences about language. Phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, stylistics and others are its branches. It is impossible to list everything that linguistics includes. Some sciences are so closely intertwined with each other that their differences are blurred, they can be children of several other sciences at the same time.

Speaking of grammar, for example, we can clearly say that it has two subsections: morphology and syntax, which, in turn, have their own branches. All of them are parts of linguistics. The language is not given to the linguist in direct observation, only the facts of speech or linguistic phenomena are directly observed, that is, the speech acts of native speakers of a living language together with their texts or linguistic material.

Linguistics involves observation; registration and description of the facts of speech; putting forward hypotheses to explain these facts; formulation of hypotheses in the form of theories and models describing the language; their

experimental verification and refutation; prediction of speech behavior. The explanation of facts can be internal through linguistic facts, or external through physiological, psychological, logical or social facts.

Empirical linguistics extracts linguistic data in two ways. First: the method of experiment - observation of the behavior of speakers of living dialects. The second way: operating with philological methods, collecting materials from written languages and interacting with philology, which studies written monuments in their cultural and historical ties.

Theoretical linguistics studies linguistic laws and formulates them in the form of theories. It can be either descriptive (describing real speech) or normative (indicating how "should" be spoken and written).

The language studied by the linguist is the language-object, and the language in which the theory is formulated is the metalanguage. The metalanguage of linguistics has its own specifics: it includes linguistic terms, names of languages and language groups, systems of special writing (transcription and transliteration).

Metatexts are created in a metalanguage - these are grammars, dictionaries, linguistic atlases, maps of the geographical distribution of languages, language textbooks, phrasebooks, etc. It is possible to speak not only about languages, but also about language in general, since the languages of the world have much in common [1, p. 37]. Private linguistics studies a single language, a group of related languages, or a pair of contacting languages.

The study of the common features of all languages empirically and deductively, the general laws of the functioning of the language, the development of methods for the study of the language is carried out by general linguistics. Its part is a typology that compares different languages regardless of the degree of their relationship and draws conclusions about the language in general. Monolingual linguistics is limited to the description of one language, but it can single out different linguistic subsystems within it and study the relationships between them. Diachronic linguistics compares different time slices in the history of a language. External linguistics describes the language in all its variety of social variants and functions. Internal linguistics considers language as a homogeneous code, where the description can be oriented towards written and oral speech; may be limited only to the "correct" language or take into account various deviations from it; can only describe a system of patterns that operate in all varieties of a language or include rules for choosing between options depending on extralinguistic factors. So linguistics is the science of language.

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